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Last workshop

Last workshop	1	The TAPAS project came to an end in September 2022. In order to meet and discuss on the achievements of the project, one last workshop was held in Antwerpen on the 8th and 9th of September.
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 [TAPAS Website](#)

ESRs

Eight ESR's over fifteen already defended their thesis.

Timothy Pommée is now a Postdoctoral Research Fellow with Yana Yunusova, affiliated to the Bulbar Function Lab (Sunnybrook Research Institute) as well as to the Speech Production Lab (University of Toronto) in Toronto, Ontario (Canada).

He works on the development and validation of a novel tool for the assessment of bulbar dysfunction in ALS.

Juan Camilo Vasquez Correa recently moved to Vicomtech a research institute in San Sebastian (Spain). He is an associate researcher working in the speech and natural language processing group, doing research on speech recognition and paralinguistics for healthcare modeling.

Tomas Arias Vergara is a Postdoc at the University Hospital Erlangen in Germany, working in the Phoniatics Department. His research focuses on analyzing voice disorders using high-speed videoendoscopy data and machine learning methods.

Zhao Ren is a postdoctoral researcher at the L3S Research Center, Leibniz University Hannover, Germany. Her research interests mainly lie in transfer learning, explainable AI, adversarial attacks, and other deep learning techniques for the computer audition applications in healthcare and wellbeing.

Yilin Pan is now working at the Department of Artificial Intelligence, the Dalian Maritime University, Dalian, China. She's doing similar work to what she did during her PhD, AI/Speech applications in Healthcare.

Srikanth Nallanthighal is currently in a position of scientist at Philips Research in Bangalore, India. He is continuing work based on his PhD topic on speech-based respiratory health sensing. He is coordinating a large data collection in collaboration with a university medical center in India. Philips will later use that data to improve the algorithms developed in his PhD.

Sebastião Quintas is working within the IRIT laboratory in Toulouse, France. He is a postdoctoral fellow implementing some of the algorithms he developed during his PhD on a clinical application.

Viviana Mendoza and **Bence Halpern** defended a few weeks ago and we wish them both great success in the future.

 [Thesis on zenodo](#)

Webinars

The TAPAS Project introduced a series of webinars each Tuesday from 1h to 2h. Each one of our ESRs presented 20 minutes + 10 minutes questions about a part of their subject (2 ESRs per slot), trying to overcome challenges encountered in the framework of TAPAS.

All the webinars were recorded and are available on our YouTube Channel

 [TAPAS YouTube Channel](#)

Selected publications

Yue Z., Loweimi E., Christensen H., Barker J., and Cvetkovic Z. *Dysarthric Speech Recognition From Raw Waveform with Parametric CNNs*. INTERSPEECH, INCHEON, KOREA, 2022

Ren Z., Chang Y., Bartl-Pokorny K.D., Pokorny, F.D., and Schuller B., *The Acoustic Dissection of Cough: Diving Into Machine Listening-based COVID-19 Analysis and Detection*. ACTA ACUSTICA 2022

Pommée T., Balaguer M., Mauclair J. Pinquier J. and Woisard V. *Criteria for creating new standard reading passages for the assessment of speech and voice: A Delphi consensus study* JOURNAL OF CLINICAL LINGUISTICS & PHONETICS 2022

Rolland T., Abad A., Cucchiari C., and Strik H. *Multilingual Transfer Learning for Children Automatic Speech Recognition* LREC, MARSEILLE, FRANCE, 2022

Halpern B. M., Feng S., van Son R., van den Brekel M., Scharenborg O. *Low-resource automatic speech recognition and error analyses of oral cancer speech*. SPEECH COMMUNICATIONS 2022

Xue W., van Hout R.W.N.M. , Cucchiari C., Strik H., *Assessing speech intelligibility of pathological speech: test types, ratings and transcription measures*, CLINICAL LINGUISTIC AND PHONETICS 2021

Mendoza Ramos V., Lowit A., Van den Steen L., Hernandez-Diaz H., Hernandez-Diaz Huici M., De Bodt M., Van Nuffelen G. *Acoustic Identification of Sentence Accent in Speakers with Dysarthria: Cross-Population Validation and Severity Related Patterns* BRAIN SCIENCES, 2021

Hermann E. and Magimai-Doss M. *Handling acoustic variation in dysarthric speech recognition systems through model combination* , INTERSPEECH,, BRNO, CZECH REPUBLIC 2021

Pérez-Toro P., Klumpp P., **Vasquez-Correa J.C.** , Schuster M., Nöth E. Orozco-Arroyave J.R. and **Arias-Vergara T.** *50 Shades of Gray: Effect of the Color Scale for the Assessment of Speech Disorders*. TEXT DIALOGUE AND SPEECH, BRNO, CZECH REPUBLIC 2022

Nallanthighal V. S., Härmä A., and Strik H., *COVID-19 detection based on respiratory sensing from speech*, INTERSPEECH, INCHEON, KOREA, 2022

Fritsch J., Magimai-Doss M. *Utterance verification-based dysarthric speech intelligibility assessment using phonetic posterior features*, . IEEE PROCESSING LETTERS 2021

Halpern B., **Fritsch J.**, **Hermann E.** , van Son R., Scharenborg O., Magimai-Doss M. *An objective framework for pathological speech synthesis* . SPEECH COMMUNICATION 2021

[Articles on zenodo](#)

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